

SOCIOPRAGMATIC NATURE OF THE FEMALE PHENOMENON IN COMMUNICATION

Feruzaxon Karimova

DSc, Senior Researcher,

Institute of Uzbek Language, Literature and Folklore,

Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Abstract

The article reveals the status and roles in Uzbek communication on the example of women's speech, the speech of the elderly and children. It also analyzes the main purpose of the use of words and phrases that reflect the softness and sincerity and kinship inherent in the national culture of the Uzbek person, using evidence from a work of art. The social, national, cultural, and spiritual aspects of the subject of communication are studied. Attention is drawn to the fact that the hidden, unexpressed aspects of women's communication, characteristic of Uzbek culture, are hidden under softness and gentleness.

Keywords: communication, female phenomenon, nationality, permanent status, temporary status.

When we touch on the topic of women in dialogue, we must first of all dwell on the status of women, and status in general. At this point, O. Hashimov's aphorism about the mother comes to mind: "If we look at a woman, first of all, as a Mother, then everything falls into place". [6:88].

Status is the place occupied by a person in the social system, and a person has the rights and responsibilities corresponding to his place in this social system. There are such statuses that are given to a person from birth to death. These are nationality, gender, race. [2:26-27]. There are so many temporary statuses that it is impossible to count them, for example, a reader when entering a library, a passenger on public transport, a stranger in another city, a patient in the presence of a doctor, a student in the presence of a teacher, a comrade in the presence of friends, a buyer in the market, a host in the presence of guests. It should be noted that this temporary status requires moving under different mental, social, and cultural influences in different situations. Not taking them into account can harm a person. If a person goes to the market and preaches about being a scholar, the seller may drive him away. Because knowledge and wealth do not require each other, but rather oppose each other.

As with every person, a woman has permanent and temporary statuses. Permanent statuses are mother, spouse, and child (in front of her parents), and the status of a sister or younger sister in front of brothers and sisters is also considered permanent. Since the boundaries of permanent statuses are clear, it is relatively easy for individuals to control their speech in them. Since temporary statuses are limitless, it is clear that in the mental, social, and cultural situation inherent in hundreds and thousands of speech environments, it is not easy for human speech to speak based on this situation. Sometimes, even in settled status, there can be social or emotional barriers.

The Russians have an over and over again aphorism taken from Voltaire's poem. It says: "Kogda ledi govorit "net", ona hochet skazat "mojet bit", kogda lady govorit "mojet bit", ona hochet skazat "da", a yesli ona govorit "da", ona ne ledi" [7]. The content is as follows. If a woman says "no", she means "maybe". A woman's "maybe" means "yes". If a woman says "yes", she is not a lady".

So, women's control of their speech depending on the situation can prevent them from lowering their most stable status, which is femininity. [4:72-76].

Below, we will analyze how the speaker, in the image of a mother in a stable status, addresses her interlocutor in the interests of her child, and what goal she pursues in the choice of address. A conversation between a mother and a female teacher who grew up in the environment of Uzbek national culture:

Sentabrning oxirlarida G'aribning o'qituvchisi – kuykanakkina juvon eshik qoqib keldi. Uzoq hol-ahvol so'rashidan va "oling-oling" qabilidagi manziratlardan so'ng, o'qituvchi:

– G'aribjon qayda, ovsin? Bir gaplashib olay degan edim, – dedi.

– Bilmasam, – dedi u yelka qisib.

– Menga aytmaydi, allaqayerlarga borib keladi. Kechqurun qaytadi, – dedi shikoyatomuz ohangda. – Nima, tag'in "ikki" oldimi? (I.Sulton. "Munojot").

(At the end of September, Garib's teacher, a young, knocked on the door. After a long inquiry about how he was doing and "take it, take it"-like greetings, the teacher said:

– Where is Garibjon, ovsin? I wanted to talk to him, – she said.

– If I don't know, – she shrugged.

– He doesn't tell me, he goes everywhere. He comes back in the evening, – said in a complaining tone. – What, did he get "two" again?)

The ovsin form of address used by the teacher in the quoted dialogue fragment serves as the initial step for the teacher to enter into a sincere dialogue with the mother of his student. In the Uzbek nation, women in the status of ovsin are usually women who communicate sincerely with each other, like friends, and sometimes, like daydreamers, who compete with each other. It is not for nothing that the proverbs "Ovsinim – ajinim, Ko'rganda kelar g'ijinim", "Ovsinlar inoq bo'lsa, Og'a-inilar chinoq bo'lmas" arose in our people. The conclusion drawn from the proverbs is this: They are competitors. They are ready to immediately point out each other's shortcomings.

Onaizor umidvor ko'zlarini juvonga tikib:

Endi nima gildik-a, singlim? – deb so'radi.

– *Siz ko'nglingizni tinch qiling, – dedi o'qituvchi. Men undagi o'zgarishlarning boisi nima ekanligini bilgani keluvdim, xolos. (I.Sulton. "Munojot")*

(The mother looked at the young woman with hopeful eyes:

What have we done now, sister? – she asked.

– You calm down, – said the teacher. I just came to find out what caused the changes in her)

The charm in the speech of the teacher and the student's mother, like a sister, which brings them closer spiritually, serves as a bond in the spiritual connection of the dialogue. We can also see from the continuation of the dialogue that the use of these forms of address helped to soften the situation and create a friendly atmosphere.

– *Mening ichimdagi bor gap shunda ekan, – so'zlanardi G'arib. – O'qib g'alati bo'lib ketdim.*

– *Aytmoqchi, o'qituvchimiz keldimi?*

– *Sen qaydan bilding? – so'radi ona.*

– *Bildim-da... Boya uyimizni so'rovdi.*

– *Hoy, o'tning yurganini qayda ko'ruvding? – dedi ona. – Opangni rosa xafa qipsan-ku? Shuncha bergan darslarim kor qilmabdi, deb ketdi. (I.Sulton. Munojot).*

(– That's what I'm saying, – said the G'aribr. – I became strange after reading.

– By the way, has our teacher come?

– How did you know? – asked the mother.

– I knew... Now asked about our house.

– Hey, did you see how the grass is growing? – said the mother. – You really hurt your sister, didn't you? She said that all the lessons I gave her didn't hurt her)

In the dialogues cited, the kinship names *ovsin*, *singil*, *opa* are introduced into the text as a form of address by the participants. In this case, these kinship terms are used pragmatically and socially to manage the communication situation.

We understand the worldview of the **mother** in the example through the words she says, that is, through her request for advice, *Endi nima qildik-a, singlim?(What did we do, sister?)* In the work, the mother's concern and anxiety about her child's mental state is combined with her simplicity and sincerity, and it is seen in her appeal to her child's teacher as if she were asking for help from a close sister.

Because "qualities such as cheerfulness, trustworthiness, simplicity, and kindness characteristic of Uzbek mothers" are reflected in the psyche of the mother's image in the work. [4:122].

The purpose of the mother's sisterly treatment of the female teacher (towards the G'arib) in the text is to teach her child to treat her teacher as a sister, not to offend her, and to treat this as disrespect for the teacher. This process is determined by the respect for the teacher in the national mentality. At the same time, it can be understood that this form of address is, under the text, an appeal to the child to study well. The form of address as a sister also evokes the content of respect in the characteristics of Uzbek national education. As a sign of closeness and respect towards a female teacher, the form of address as a sister also exists in the Andijan environment. We know well that in different social

regions a female teacher is addressed differently. For example, "oye" (mother) is used in Namangan, "opa" (sister) is used in Andijan, "opo'ov" (sister) is used in Fergana, and in Khorezm, the same *domla* (sisterly) form of address is used for both female and male teachers. Under the influence of the Soviet regime, for a certain period of time, forms of address such as "o'rtoq" (comrade) and "tovarish" (comrade) were also used.

"According to Uzbek national and cultural customs, we can often observe that women, even to express sincerity, address strangers or non-relatives as sister, daughter-in-law, owner, aunt, depending on their age." [3:140].

Literary scholar I. Hakqul said: "Words educate a person. All positive and negative qualities inherent in a person are reflected in words." [5:4]. In particular, in the lively speech of the Uzbek language, which is imbued with national education, we can see through many examples that the female and male images of the participants in their social roles acquire respect, softness and firmness. W. von Humboldt's thoughts about the national spirit and the national language, "Language is, as it were, the outer appearance of the spirit of a people" [2:83] have not lost their validity over the centuries.

In studying the process of communication, it is necessary to pay special attention to the influence of national and social colorings on the speech of women and men. The sincerity in women's speech, as well as cunning, and adaptation to the environment for the benefit of their children and family, are noticeably reflected in their communication. In conclusion, female forms of address in communication convey the content of the message about the linguistic world to which the speaker belongs, its landscape, the characteristics of the territory in which she lives, and at the same time, the personal, individual world, and social identity of the speaker.

References

1. Belyanin V.P., Shkuratova I.P. Dialogi o cheloveke govoryashim i pishushim. – SPb.: Rech, 2011. – C. 26–27.
2. Gumboldt V. fon. Izbranniye trudi po yazikoznaniyu. – Moskva: Progress, 1984. – S. 83.
3. Iskandarova Sh.M. O'zbek nutq odatining muloqot shakllari: Filol. fan. nomz. ... diss. – Samarqand, 1993. – 140 b.
4. Karimova F. O'zbek tilidagi muloqot matnlarining pragmatolingvistik va psixolingvistik xususiyatlari. – Toshkent: Bookmany print, 2025. – 188b.
5. Umurzaqova M. Badiiy matnda lisoniy shaxs voqelanishining sotsiopragsmatik va lingvomadaniy aspekti. Filol. fan. d-ri (DSc) ...diss. – Toshkent. 2024. – B. 122.
6. Haqqul I. "Ne nazmki o'tlug' ko'nguldin chiqordim...?"// Abadiyat farzandlari. – Toshkent: Yosh gvardiya, 1990. – B. 4.
7. Hoshimov O'. Daftar hoshiyasidagi bitiklar. – Toshkent: Yangi asr avlodi, 2018. – B. 88.
8. <https://lems.sg.spu.ru> > mod_folder > content >